

Marine Fishers and Community Transformations: A Case Study of Mofusbandar Village

1. Dr. Pilli Vasanthi and 2. Dr. Kodi Srinivasu

1. Department of Anthropology,
Andhra University, Visakhapatnam, Andhra Pradesh

2. Post-Doctoral Fellow-ICSSR, Department of Anthropology, Andhra University,
Visakhapatnam, Andhra Pradesh

Received: Sep 15, 2025

Accepted: Oct 06, 2025

Published: Oct 09, 2025

ABSTRACT

This study examines the socio-cultural, democratic and educational transformations within the fishing communities of Mofusbandar village, located in the Srikakulam District of North Coastal Andhra Pradesh, South India. It focuses on how these communities have evolved over the years, underlining the socio-democratic and educational shifts that have occurred over the decades. In particular, the study explores the impact of recent interventions, especially in infrastructure and education, contributing to notable changes in the community's way of life. Based on anthropological fieldwork, this research provides insights into these coastal fishing communities' ongoing development and transformation, emphasizing the resilience and adaptability of these communities in the face of change.

Keywords: Development, Economy, Education, Fishing Communities, Transformation

INTRODUCTION

In Indian social research, the village has long been regarded as a fundamental unit for understanding socio-cultural and economic organization networks, particularly among rural communities. Such studies have played a crucial role in conceptualizing key social processes, including Sanskritization and the concept of the dominant caste (Srinivas, 1955), caste hierarchies (Dube, 1960; Dumont & Pocock, 1957), and the Jajmani system (Wiser, 1936). The Census of India, during its 1950–51 survey operations, produced several village ethnographies that emphasized the socio-economic and cultural fabric of these rural societies. The early village studies have created theoretical frameworks for considering change and continuity in village life. Among these monographs, the study of Mofusbandar, a fishing village in the Srikakulam district

of Andhra Pradesh on the coast of the Bay of Bengal, has been utilized as a benchmark in the present research to assess the current socio-economic status of fishermen. The studies also revealed that over the past sixty years, the economy of Mofusbandar has not changed much and continues to be marginalized among the fishing communities. However, intermittent acquisitions in education and training have begun to yield returns, gradually empowering the youth. This shift has fostered a growing belief among fishermen in the transformative power of education. As a result, most children are now enrolled in public and private schools. Further, studies among the fishing communities provide various aspects of these communities. The primary emphasis of recent studies documented the healthcare and healing (Pukkalla & Sharma 2018, 2020a) and fishermen and their plurality of deities (Vijaya Prakash, 2022), livelihoods (Rama Mohan 2016; Pukkalla & Rama Mohan, 2021), fishers' knowledge and contribution to their economies (Pukkalla & Sharma, 2020b; Kodi, 2021) by integrating resilience perspectives to draw scholarly contributions to these small-scale fishing communities and their developmental dimensions (Vasanthi et al 2015; Pukkalla & Rama Mohan 2023; Nikku et al, 2024; Pukkalla and Gangadhar 2025).

METHODOLOGY

This study is based on ethnographic fieldwork, employing a random sampling design. The research focused on Mofusbandar, a fishing village in the Srikakulam District, examining various socio-cultural parameters. For an in-depth analysis of navigation practices and fishing paraphernalia, two villages or habitations were selected from each urban, semi-urban, and rural category. Both qualitative and quantitative data were collected, systematically organized into tables, and incorporated into the text where relevant. This approach enhances the study by integrating the social and cultural dimensions of the fishing communities.

All fishing hamlets/villages under the Mofusbandar revenue village are considered for the study. A total sample of 412 households is selected from six hamlets/villages for the comparative study. The purposive and random sampling methods are used to cover all the variations that are noticed among the fishers of the selected habitations. Of 412 households, 83 belong to the Jalari and 329 to the Vadabalija communities. Among the Jalari sample, 32 households belong to Jalaripeta, while the remaining 51 belong to Khazipeta. In the case of Vadabalija, all four

villages are considered. Village-wise selection is again based on variation among the community in terms of assets and economic activity/. Of 329 households, 111 are from Chinna Ganagalla Peta, 99 from Pedda Ganagalla Peta, 82 from Pukkallapeta, and 37 from Narasayyapeta. Thereby, the total sample for the analysis comes to 490, which includes 78 households of the past secondary study and 412 of the present primary study.

Name of the Village	Past Population/(HH)	Present Population/(HH)	Community-wise Population/ (HH)
Jalaripeta	-	198 (32)	381 (83)-Jalari
Khazipeta	57 (10)	183 (51)	
Chinna Ganagalla Peta	-	371 (111)	1414 (329)- Vadabalija
Pedda Ganagalla Peta	276 (68)	532 (99)	
Pukkallapeta	-	369 (82)	
Narasayyapeta	-	142 (37)	
Total	333 (78)	1795 (412)	

In addition to the Census of India Monographs, which were brought out in two spells, 1961 and 1981, and other statistical information from the reports and the Fisheries department data, a predesigned schedule is canvassed among households. The information is sought verbally from the informants at their house or workplace (beach). Face-to-face interviews are undertaken while the heads of households are in the midst of family members or working partners. The sought information is cross-verified with the village functionaries, relatives, and neighbours. The critical information related to house maintenance, household assets, fish vending, fishing, and knowledge on maritime resources and tenancy is sought through focus group discussions. Case study methods are also used to authenticate the observations.

MOFUSBANDAR PROFILE- THE PAST TO PRESENT

Mofusbandar village comprises two castes, Jalari and Vadabalija, in six separate hamlets. Jalari live in Khazipeta and Jalaripet, while Vadabalija live in Chinna Ganagalla Peta, Pedda Ganagalla Peta, Pukkallapeta, and Narasayyapeta. The census monograph survey was confined to two hamlets, the Khazipeta representing Jalari and Pedda Ganagalla Peta by Vadabalija. The main village inhabitants belong to the communities of Vaisya, Chakali, Telaga, Golla, Mala, and Madiga. However, they are not considered for the study as the survey's primary purpose was to study the social and economic set-up of a village mainly dependent on fishing.

Jalaripeta

Jalaripeta hamlet is a few meters away from the south of the Mofusbandar main village near the Langulya River. The Jalari caste solely inhabits Jalaripeta. According to the 1961 Census House list, 32 households, or 11.15% of the total village households, and 128 persons, or 9.48% of the total village population, reside in this hamlet. The main occupation of the residents is fishing.

Khazipeta

This hamlet is located on the slope of a small sand mound, east of the Mofusbandar main village at a distance of about a kilometre. It is surrounded by a sprawling sand yard and an array of casuarina groves. The sea laves the land in the east at a distance of about half a mile. The houses are laid out facing each other in one lane from north to south. According to the 1961 Census House list, 14 households forming 4.26% and 62 persons forming 4.59% of the village population are in this hamlet.

Chinna Ganagalla Peta

Chinna Ganagalla Peta hamlet is about 700 meters east of the main village between Khazipeta and Peddaganagallapeta. The surroundings of this hamlet are the same as those of Khazipeta. The houses are laid out in a few lanes and clusters and are wholly inhabited by people from the Vadabaliya caste, whose main occupation is fishing. According to the 1961 Census House list, 54 households, 16.47% of village households, and 142 persons, 10.52% of the village population, live here.

Pedda Ganagalla Peta

This hamlet is located 800 meters from the main village on a slightly raised sand mound on the way to Mofusbandar *Revu* (harbour) from the main village. The surroundings of this hamlet are the same as those of Khazipeta. The houses are arranged in lines, besides a few being laid out in clusters, and are wholly inhabited by the Vadabaliya caste. According to the 1961 Census House list, 90 households, 27.35 % of village households, and 329 persons, 24.37 % of the village population, reside in this hamlet. The main occupation of the inhabitants of this hamlet is fishing.

Pukkallapeta

This hamlet is situated just by the side of Peddaganagallapeta on a raised sand bed by the east-tern bank of the Uppugedda and nearer to the Langulya River. The houses are laid out in lines and clusters. According to the 1961 Census House list, 58 households' form 17.62% of village households, and 277 persons, with 20.52% of the total village population, inhabit this hamlet. The population belongs to the Vadabaliya caste, who depend mainly on fishing for their livelihood.

Narasayyapeta

This tiny hamlet has recently sprung up near the east sea shore, about a mile from the main village. It was reported that the residents of this hamlet migrated from Dibbaluru, a nearby coastal fishermen's habitation area, due to some tensions between fishermen and other groups. The houses are arranged in a small row. According to the 1961 Census House list, eight households forming 2.43% of village households and 45 persons forming 3.33 % of the village population are in this hamlet.

Connectivity Infrastructure

Mofusbandar village is connected by a metalled road from Srikakulam town to Kallepalle village. Regular private motor transport services from Srikakulam up to Kallepalle village, the bus terminus, are available. From this terminus, one has to walk along the road (about a kilometer) up to Mofusbandar main village or go by a bullock cart. The cycle rickshaws are also available at Srikakulam and Kallepalle, which negotiate the distance to Mofusbandar main village. Proceeding towards the fishermen hamlets, one has to cross the *Uppugedda* (salty stream), where the depth varies from 2 to 4 feet. A slender bridge made out of logs allows only a single man with very light luggage to cross at a time. However, men and women with heavy loads of fish on their heads cross *Uppugedda*, wading through knee-deep and sometimes waist-deep water. If the casual visitor is reluctant to an awkward crossing in the thigh-deep water that requires lifting the clothes, a catamaran (*theppa*) must be engaged. Just after crossing the backwaters, one has to pass through the sand yards to reach the fishermen's hamlets. To reach the sea shore, one has to walk a distance of about half a kilometre and cross a small sheet of sea

backwaters in a catamaran (*theppa*) or a boat. The main village, as well as the fishermen's hamlets, are not electrified.

As per the census report, basic facilities other than houses and settlement alignment are a water source, a school, a post office, and a market. These are presented in table form to aid in understanding the status of the field area.

Village/Hamlet	Water Source	Market	School	Post Office
Jalaripeta	Open well at main village-Mofusbandar	Main village-Mofusbandar	Elementary School between Pukkallapeta and Pedda Ganagalla Peta	Experimental Post Office located at main village
Khazipeta	Natural Spring	Main village-Mofusbandar		
Chinna Ganagalla Peta	Well in the hamlet	Kirana shop maintained by main village trader		
Pedda Ganagalla Peta	Well between Pukkallapeta and Chinna Ganagalla Peta, and Natural spring	Retail shop and Tea shop maintained by the main village traders (Vysya)		
Pukkallapeta		Provisions Shop maintained by the main village trader		
Narsaiahpeta	Natural Spring	Main village and Kallepalle		

Place of Worship and Crematorium

The report also presents significant information about places of worship and crematoriums. All the hamlets and the main village do not have a common place of worship or a common cremation or burial ground. On the contrary, each has its own places of worship, deities, and cremation or burial ground. As one proceeds towards the fishermen hamlets of Pedda Ganagalla Peta and Pukkallapeta, crossing the *Uppugedda*, a shrine dedicated to Bhoolokamma (Goddess of the Earth) is seen near Pukkallapeta. Mostly, Pukkallapeta residents worship this deity. The intensive survey of the two hamlets, viz, Khazipeta and Pedda Ganagalla Peta, showed that on the northern side of Pedda Ganagalla Peta, there is in the casuarina grove a common place where the female deity commonly known as Ammoru or the Mother is worshipped by all the residents of the hamlet of Pedda Ganagalla Peta only. There are other spots also on the sand mounds on the outskirts of the hamlets where the *Ammoru* (deity) is worshipped. In Khazipeta, some common ad hoc places of worship in Casuarina Grove and on sand mounds where the inhabitants offer their worship on occasion, like Danappa and Korlasatti Sambaram. The cremation ground

is located separately towards the northern side of the hamlet at a distance of a few yards on the sandy yard.

Against this background, as per the aim and objectives of this study, the data were extracted from the Census of India Monographs of 1961 and 1981, and the present primary data were collected among the Jalari and Vadabaliya fishing communities. Keeping the extracted data as a benchmark, the present data is compared to qualify the study as diachronic.

GEOGRAPHICAL AND SOCIO-ECONOMIC PROFILE OF MOFUSBANDAR FISHERMEN'S VILLAGE CLUSTER

Mofusbandar- a fishermen's village cluster is situated at 18°13'45" northern latitude and 83°56'28" eastern longitude on the coastal land of the Bay of Bengal. The cluster is bounded by Ippili village in the northeast, the Bay of Bengal in the east and south, Nagavali in the southwest, and Kallepalle village in the west and north-west. The land surface of the village gently slopes from west to east and south-east towards *Uppugedda*, a small streamlet joining the backwaters of the Bay of Bengal. The *Uppugedda*, which flows from north-east to south before joining the backwater of the Bay and the Nagavali River, divides the inland arable land and the coastal dunes. The eastern and the south-eastern planks are rich in sand accumulations and have casuarina plantations.

Mofusbandar, a traditional Indian village of Kallepalle Panchayat of Srikakulam district of north coastal Andhra Pradesh, is located on the left bank of the Nagavali River adjoining the Bay of Bengal. A cluster of seven hamlets, now transformed into revenue villages, spread over the sandy stretches of the sea coast. A series of sand ridges divides and protects human habitations spread over three square kilometres from the sea. Mofusbandar is a multi-caste village with a colony. Jalari, a traditional fishing community, inhabits the colony of Mofusbandar and Khazipet village.

In contrast, the other five villages, namely Pukkallapeta, Pedda Ganagalla Peta, Chinna Ganagalla Peta, and Narasayyapeta, are inhabited exclusively by the Vadabaliya fishing community. Jalari and Vadabaliya endogamous groups' main occupation is fishing, and they appear similar in many ways, but they segregate for habitation. These two

communities fish in both the Bay of Bengal's marine waters and the Nagavali River's brackish waters. These clusters of villages are connected by road to inland villages and Srikakulam town, the headquarters of Srikakulam district. The fisherwomen of this cluster of villages regularly vend fish in neighbouring villages and towns. The land surface of the village gently slopes from west to east and south-east towards *Uppugedda*, a small streamlet joining the backwaters of the Bay of Bengal. The *Uppugedda*, which flows from north-east to south before joining the backwater of the Bay and the Nagavali River, divides the inland arable land and the coastal dunes. Now, a bridge has been constructed over the *Uppugedda* stream.

All six fishermen's villages/habitations come under the Kallepalli Panchayat Samithi administrative jurisdiction of Gara mandal of Srikakulam Zillah Parishad, with its headquarters in Srikakulam town. This cluster of villages is about 12 km east of Srikakulam town, about 7 km from Gara village, the Mandal headquarters, and about a km from Kallepalli village, the Panchayat headquarters. A Police Station with jurisdiction over this village is in Srikakulam town, the nearest centre for consumer durables, household items, medical services, and such allied services. The nearest industrial and commercial centres are at Srikakulam and Amadalavalasa, the latter of which is also the railhead. The fishermen visit shops in their habitations or go to Mofusbandar or some-times Kallepalle village, besides Srikakulam town, for purchases.

Village	Water Source	Schools	Anganwadi	Shops	Shrines/ Temple	Public Offices
Jalaripeta	Overhead Tank	Elementary School	Sub Centre	Provisions shops-2	Rama Temple-1	Panchayat Office, Ration Depot, Community Hall, Shore Shed, Dry Fishing Yard, Cyclone Relief Centre, Fish drying platforms one each to all 6 villages
	Open well-1			Tea shops- 2	Church-1	
	Borewell-1					
Khazipeta	Overhead Tank	Elementary School	Sub Centre	Provisions shops-3	Shrine-1	
	Borewell-1					
Chinna Ganagalla Peta	Overhead Tank	Elementary School	Main Centre	Provisions shps-2	Ram Temple-1	
	Open well-1 Borewells-2				Shrines-1	
Pedda Ganagalla Peta	Overhead Tank, Open wells-2	Elementary School-1	Main Centre	Provisions shops-3	Ram Temple-1 Shrines-2	
	Borewells-2	High School-1			Wine shop- 1	Hanuman Temple-1

				Tea shop-1	
Pukkallapeta	Overhead Tank,	Elementary School	Main Centre	Provisions shops-3	Ram Temple-1
	Open well-1				Shrines-2
	Borewells-				
Narsaiahpeta	Tap Connection from Khazipeta Overhead Tank	Elementary School	Sub Centre	Provisions shps-2	Ram Temple-1
	Borewell-1				

TRANSFORMATIONS AND COMMUNITY PARTICIPATION: THE PAST AND PRESENT

Four hundred twelve households are consulted to elicit information through a pre-designed schedule on various facets of social, economic, political, and cultural aspects of fishers' way of life. The collected data, in addition to the data from the Census of India Monographs, is tabulated as per the parameters required against the objectives of the thesis and is presented in the following pages:

The Past

Household size

All the 362 persons of the two hamlets under survey are Hindus and belong to the Jalari (58 persons) and Vadabalija (304 persons) castes (table 3). Among the Jalari, the average size of a household is 5.8. Two households have 2 to 3 members, 5 have 4 to 6 members, and 2 have 7 to 9 members, while only one has 11 members. Among the Vadabalija, the average size of households is 4.47 and ranges from 2 to 3 member households, with a frequency of 21 households, from 4 to 6 members, with a frequency of 39 households. 7 Households are found in the Household size of 7 to 9 members, and only 1 Household with a size of 13 members. There are no single-member Households. Overall, 67 Households (85.9%) fall in the range of 2 to 6 members. Among the fishermen surveyed, the average household size for both castes is 4.64.

Household size (The Past and Present-Jalari)

Fishing Community-Household Sample/Village	Male Unmarried Children	Female Unmarried Children	Married Male Children	Married Female Children	Dependent Parents	Total	Family Size
Past-10 HH	17	9	15	16	1	58	5.8
Jalari (KP)	-4.7	-2.49	-4.14	-4.42	-0.28	-16.02	
Past-68 HH	82	60	66	68	28	304	4.5
Vadabalija (PP)	-22.65	-16.57	-18.23	-18.78	-7.73	-83.98	
Sub-Total	99	69	81	84	29	362	4.6
	-27.35	-19.06	-22.38	-23.2	-8.01	-100	
Present-83 HH	114	66	86	94	21	381	4.6
Jalari (JP & KP)	-6.35	-3.68	-4.79	-5.24	-1.17	-21.23	
Present-329 HH Vadabalija (CG, PG, PP, NP)	337	273	356	374	74	1414	4.3
	-18.77	-15.21	-19.83	-20.84	-4.12	-78.77	
Sub-Total	451	339	442	468	95	1795	4.4
	-25.13	-18.89	-24.62	-26.07	-5.29	-100	

JP=Jalaripeta, KP= Khazipeta, CG= Chinna Ganagalla Peta, PG=Pedda Ganagalla Peta, PP=Pukkallapata, NP= Narasayyapeta

Figures in the parenthesis indicate per cent

The data in the table indicates that there is a change in family size. The change is more striking among Jalari from 5.8 to 4.6 than among Vadabalija, which is 4.5 to 4.3. On average, the family size declined from 4.6 to 4.4. The demographic profile data indicate that unmarried male children (27.35% and 25.13%) are more common than female unmarried children (19.06% and 18.89%). In comparison, among married children, females (23.20% and 26.07%) are more than males (22.38% and 24.62%) among the sample Jalari and Vadabalija populations, respectively. Aged parents classified as dependents are more in the past (8.01%) than in the present (5.29%). The children and the aged data are pertinent in continuing traditional marine fishing activity, as the knowledge accumulated over the years on participatory experience needs to be transmitted to successive generations. The informal knowledge of the aged, coupled with the formal education of the present, goes a long way in continuing traditional marine fishing. The demographic profile of the study villages is within the frame of the continuance of age-old activity. Most of the married children are contributing to the fishing economy. The married males accompany the father in sailing and fishing, while the females attend to domestic chores and fish vending. The married children are shown in the table to calculate the family size. As far as the fishing

economy is concerned, they are independent earners and a nuclear family. No joint family is recorded in the sample.

Housing Transitions and Infrastructural Progress

The fishermen's houses give an appearance of huts. They are built on the sandy mounts in continuous rows but are compartmentalized into individual houses. For living purposes, they have only one floor, i.e., the ground floor. A narrow upper storey, locally known as an *atika*, is used only as a storage place. All the fishermen's houses are used as residences. The size and plinth area depend on the size of the household and are very much conditioned by the close neighbourhood of the fishermen, closely related to kinship ties. The construction mode is conditioned by the locally available housing raw material, viz, mud for walls and paddy straw for roofs. The necessity for a new house arises only when the old house has to be discarded, or a new family is set up, or the strength of the family increases. Two types of houses are found among the fishermen community of Peda Ganagalla Peta and Khazipeta hamlets. These house types are locally known as *vasillu* and *chuttilli (gudisillu)*. Both these types are found among the Vadabaliya caste, where only the *vasillu* type has been built by the Jalari caste. There are 63 *vasillu* and five *chuttillu* belonging to the Vadabaliya caste in Pedda Ganagalla Peta, and all the 10 houses among Jalaris are *vasillu* type.

Fishermen's houses do not exhibit elaborate or impressive decorations or drawings on the doors, walls, and floor. In some houses, however, the door frames and doors carry one or two lotus flowers carved on them. The threshold and the walls up to 1 foot from the ground level are bordered with red earth for decorative purposes. After smearing the floor with thin cow dung water, *muggu* (rangavalli drawings made on the floor with lime powder) is drawn on special occasions. The *muggu* designs are very simple and crude. Common among them are *sankhu* (the conch shell) and *chakra* (the wheel). Walls are whitewashed 2 to 5 times a year, generally on the festival days like Sankranti, Sivaratri, Gandhamasi, Chavithiamasi, and Avitidasami.

Housing has been one of the important parameters to assess the socio-economic and cultural status of the family. As described in the chapter on fishermen's habitations, the villages of Mofusbandar are also congested for various reasons. The sea on the eastern and *Uppugedda*

on the western, and the Nagavali river on the south, together with dunes in the form of ridges, are a few contributing to the congestion. Due to these reasons, the settlement pattern, hitherto clustered, has become linear. The houses of the sampled villages are of different types, such as thatched huts, tiled and asbestos-roofed houses, and concrete buildings. A moderate Fishermen house comprises a bedroom (on average 75 square feet), a similar dimension living space, and a small kitchen (5x4 feet). Most of the houses are constructed with the government's support under various schemes over time. Built houses in the form of a colony, providing construction materials like steel, cement, and door and window frames on subsidy, have been utilized by the fishers. The housing data related to 412 sampled households is collected and presented.

Hosing of the Past and Present

Fishing Community	Thatched house	Sheeted House	Concrete House
Past-10 HH	10	0	0
Jalari (KP)	-100		
Past-68 Vadabalija	68	0	0
(PP)	-100		
Sub-Total	78	0	0
	-100		
Present-83	4	7	72
Jalari (JP & KP)	-4.82	-8.43	-86.75
Present-329 Vadabalija (CG, PG, PP, NP)	23	7	299
	-6.1	-2.13	-90.88
Sub Total	27	14	371
	-6.55	-3.4	-90.05

At the time of the Census of India survey, all houses were of thatched traditional houses, either *vasillu* or *chuttillu*. Data from the present study indicates that only 6.55 percent of the houses are traditional, while the remaining are sheet-roofed houses (3.40%) and concrete buildings (90.05%). A marginal percentage of tiled (5.72%) and sheeted houses (5.13%) are noticed among the fishermen. The community-wise housing variation is marginal and shows no significant pattern. Though the traditional conical thatched roofs on circular mud walls adapt to maritime weather and vagaries, the fishermen's current adaptation is the permanency and

fireproof nature of steel and cement. Concrete structures are an adaptation to overcome space congestion, where traditional houses occupy larger spaces. The graphic representation of housing types clearly shows the paradigm shift in housing patterns from traditional thatched houses to modern concrete structures for living. The shift is similar in the Jalari and Vadabalija communities, with a thin transition of sheeted houses.

Participation in Democratic Governance and Fishing Communities

Political participation in democratic processes is inevitable and mandatory per the Indian Constitution. Political representation is based on community and gender. Other qualifications like education, experience, skill, etc, are not necessary to participate in democratic processes. Thereby, any person can participate in political service. In order to understand the political awareness and participation of fishermen in the study area, data related to households and spouses is sought, as there is gender reservation. Of 412 households and their spouses, only 14 (3.4%) people are represented in political institutions. These representations are seen only at the village, Mandal, and district levels. Their representation at the state level is zero. However, two members, one from Jalari and Vadabalija, are (Mandal Parishad Territorial Constituency) MPTC members, and women under the women's quota represent these. One Vadabalija male member is a Zilla Parishad Territorial Constituency (ZPTC). No Member of Legislative Assembly (MLA) is represented from the study area.

Educational Attainment as a Driving Force for Community Development

Education is a stabilizer of culture, whereby culture is transmitted from one generation to another; thus, it maintains continuity and is an instrument for adaptation and change (Spindler, 1987). Education takes various forms. Parents pass on accumulated knowledge and information to their children. Children also get education from the people they come in contact with and gain something through observing things around them. All experiences human beings gain in enculturation can be called informal education. Formal education passes on this accumulated knowledge and information in an organized and systematic manner, while simultaneously developing the receivers' abilities to acquire knowledge for future generations. It aims to enhance the child's reading, writing, and understanding abilities.

Education has been one of the powerful engines that propel an individual's development and growth, affecting the family and community. It influences production and increases income, thereby improving the well-being of the family and the community. Marine fishing is often believed to be an economic activity carried out by illiterate fishermen or people with low literacy. The data related to education status is collected among the sampled households, their wives, children, and dependents (parents or in-laws of the head of the household). The collected data is categorized into three groups representing the past generation (old parents and in-laws of the head of the household), the present generation (head of the households and their spouses), and the future generation (children, both unmarried and married) of fishermen of the study area. The three-tier categorization aims to understand the generational attitude towards education, as in recent years, the universalization of primary education and the Right to Education have been the priorities of the governments. In addition, the investigator noticed that the young children were going to schools and convents near the fishermen's villages. The collected data is presented in the following two tables to present the data generation-wise and the four-fold division.

Education status of Sample Fishermen

Fishing Community/ No of HH / Villages	Illiterate	< 5 th Std	6-7 th Std	8-10 th std	Inter	UG	Diploma	Total
Past-10 HH	9	1	0	0	0	0	0	10
Jalari (KP)	-11.54	-1.28						-12.82
Past-68 Vadabalija	62	6	0	0	0	0	0	68
(PP)	-79.49	-7.69						-87.18
Sub-Total	71	7	0	0	0	0	0	78
	-91.03	-8.97						-100
Present-83	49	18	11	5	0	0	0	83
Jalari (JP & KP)	-11.89	-4.37	-2.67	-1.21				-20.15
Present-329 Vadabalija (CG, PG, PP, NP)	201	47	21	51	7	2	0	329
	-48.78	-11.41	-5.1	-12.37	-1.7	-0.49		-79.85
Sub Total	250	65	32	56	7	2	0	412
	-60.67	-15.78	-7.77	-13.59	-1.7	-0.49		-100

Out of the total population of 362, only 12 are literate; all 173 females are illiterate. Among the 12 literate males, nine are literate without any formal education. At the same time, three have completed only primary or junior introductory courses, and the remaining three are 25-59 years

old. Among the nine literates again, five are school-going children below 14 years, three are aged more than 25 and less than 59 years, while one is aged 60 years. Among these literates, except one male in the Jalari caste, all the remaining 11 belong to the Vadabalija caste only. This proves the absolute backwardness of these communities, particularly the Jalaris. The second report, 1981, presents a marginal number of matriculates (Jalari-2 and Vadabalija-28) among all age groups.

CONCLUSION

The results of the earlier study, Mofusbandar, a fishing village complex by the Census of India during 1961 and 1981, are compared under the present study to assess the development and change between the two study periods. Both studies have covered the Jalari and Vadabalija fishermen communities in their various facets of life. The past sample consists of Jalari 10 and Vadabalija 68, while the present sample consists of Jalari 83 and Vadabalija 329 on a prorate basis. It is also observed that there is a reduction in family size from 4.5 to 4.3, more striking among Jalari (5.8 to 4.6) than the Vadabalija (4.5 to 4.3). The demographic profile indicates that unmarried male children are more (25.13%) than female (18.89%), while among married children, females (26.07%) are more than males (24.62%), indicating continuity of the past trend. The married males accompany the father in sailing and fishing, while females attend to domestic chores and fish vending, but they are independent as far as the family is concerned. No joint family is recorded in the sample.

During the past survey, only one elementary school used to take care of fishermen's children, but now six elementary schools, one each in all six sampled villages. One High School located at Pedda Ganagalla Peta extends upward linkages to the elementary school pass outs. In addition to these schools, one elementary school on a convent model is being operated in the private sector. The distribution analysis of parents and their children's past and present education status clearly presents a phenomenal educational change. There has been a rapid change in the aspirations and attitudes of the fishers as indicated by the total illiteracy of the 1960s, which had become literate and educated to the tune of a graduation by 2016. The Jalari and Vadabalija show the same trend in pursuance, but are slightly smaller in Jalari than in Vadabalija. If the similar trend continues, more people would be in higher and professional education.

At the time of the Census of India survey, all houses were of thatched traditional houses, either *vasillu* or *chuttillu*. At present, only 6.55 percent are traditional houses. The new house types are sheet-roofed (3.40%) and concrete buildings (90.05%). The community-wise housing variation is marginal and does not show any significant pattern. Though the traditional conical thatched roofs on circular mud walls adapt to maritime weather and vagaries, the fishermen's current adaptation is steel and cement's permanency and fireproof nature. In addition, the adoption of concrete structures is to overcome space congestion, where traditional houses occupy larger spaces.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We sincerely thank our supervisors, Prof. P. Vijaya Prakash and Prof. Jai Kishan, for their invaluable support and encouragement throughout the doctoral program. Our heartfelt thanks go to the fishing communities of the study area for their time, patience, and cooperation during the fieldwork.

REFERENCES

- Dube, S. C. (1960). A Deccan village. In M. N. Srinivas (Ed.), *India's village*. London, Asia Publishing House (first published in 1955).
- Dumont, L., & Peacock, D. F. (Eds.). (1957). Village studies and kinship. *Contributions to Indian Sociology*, 1, 23–64.
- Kodi, S. (2021). Indigenous Knowledge and Engaging Marine Fishing Practices in North Coastal Andhra Pradesh. *Anthropologist*, 44(1-3), 1-9.
- Nikku, B. R., Galimberti, S., Gurung, K., & Kodi, S. (2025). International social work, community science, and disaster justice. In *Pushing boundaries in social work around the world, Vol. 2: Policy and global perspectives* (pp. 29–42). Springer Nature Switzerland.
- Pukkalla, D., & Gangadhar, M. R. (2025). Marine ecological adaptation and fishing livelihoods in a South Indian fishing community. *The Eastern Anthropologist*, 78(1–2), 151–160.
- Pukkalla, D., & Rama Moahn, K.R. (2023). Marine Fishing Community in South India and Impacts of Technological Transformation. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Rural Development*, 32(2), 196-206.

- Pukkalla, D., & Rama Mohan, K. R. (2021). Local knowledge and marine livelihoods among the South Indian fishing community. *Journal of Asian and African Studies*, 56(3), 549–557.
- Pukkalla, D., & Sharma, B. V. (2020a). Divinatory functionaries and expansion of healing systems among the South Indian fishing community. *Man In India*, 100(1–2), 125–135.
- Pukkalla, D., & Sharma, B. V. (2020b). Transmission and erosion of local knowledge practices in a fishing village in South India. *Journal of Ecological Anthropology*, 22(1), 34–42.
- Pukkalla, D., & Sharma, B. V. (2018). Occupational health risks and etiologies among the Jalari community of northern districts in Andhra Pradesh. *Journal of Human Ecology*, 61(1-3), 64–71.
- Rama Mohan, K. R. (2016). Livelihood and migration of a marine fishing community. *Journal of Indian Anthropological Society*, 51, 60–68.
- Srinivas, M. N. (1955). The social structure of a Mysore village. In M. Marriott (Ed.), *Village India* (pp. 1–35). University of Chicago Press.
- Vasanthi, P and Venkatalakshmi, V and Murali Mohan, M (2015). Fishing fathers, vending mothers and educated youth (A maritime community on east coast of India in transition). *International Journal of Current Research*, 7 (10). pp. 21097-21100.
- Vijaya Prakash, P. (2022). Plurality of deities and maritime religion. *Indian Anthropologist*, 52(1–2), 1–20.
- Wisner, W. H. (1936). *The Hindu Jajmani system: A socio-economic system interrelating members of a Hindu village community in services*. Lucknow Publishing House.